

Silicon Carbide Power Device Status and Issue

Fritz J. Kub, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—In this paper, the status and issues of primary silicon carbide devices types are reviewed. The device types reviewed include SiC MOSFET, JFET, bipolar, IGBT, thyristor and JBS diodes. In addition, the key issues relating SiC material to device reliability and performance are identified.

Index Terms—Bipolar transistor, insulated gate bipolar transistors, JFETs, power MOSFETs, power semiconductor devices, power transistor, Schottky diode, semiconductor epitaxial layers, silicon carbide, thyristor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Significant progress has been made in both SiC power device decade and SiC material technology over the last decade. Key to this advance has been the basic and applied research in understanding the key issues in both material and devices and finding solution to the issues. While not all material and device issue have resolved, there has been sufficient progress in finding solutions that there has been the recent commercial introduction of both 1200 V SiC MOSFET and 1200V SiC JFET switches. While SiC has shown significant advantages compared to silicon power device technology at 1200V, even larger benefits are expected at higher voltages. This paper discusses both the status of 1200V power switches and the progress is being made in higher voltage power switches.

II. SILICON CARBIDE POWER DEVICES

A. SiC MOSFET

Currently, SiC MOSFETs are being developed for 1200 V and higher voltage operation. The advantages of the SiC MOSFETs include high switching speed, low switching loss, high voltage capability, positive temperature coefficient which enables paralleling in modules, and the potential for high operation temperatures. Significant progress has been made in SiC MOSFET devices and technology with the first commercial SiC 1200V MOSFET being introduced in 2011 [1].

The state-of-the-art at lower voltages is a 1500V 4H-SiC DMOSFET with an on-resistance of 3.7 m Ω -cm² with a gate bias of 20 V [2]. The device was successfully scaled to 7 mm x 8 mm chip size (active area = 0.5 cm²) and the resulting device showed a drain current of 377 A at a forward voltage

drop of 3.8 V. In an inductive load switching configuration, the SiC DMOSFET showed a switching loss of 6.82 mJ per cycle when controlling 120 kW of power (600 V, 200 A). Other SiC MOSFETs that have been developed for lower voltage operation include a 1400V SiC MOSFET with an on-resistance of 5 m Ω -cm² [3]. The state-of-the-art for SiC MOSFET modules at lower voltages is a 1200V, 800 module that incorporates twenty 80A MOSFET and twenty 50A SiC Junction Barrier Schottky diodes [4]. This module demonstrated a 59 percent reduction in total inverter loss for a test condition with engine coolant at 100oC and 10kHz switching.

At intermediate voltages, a 3300V SiC DMOSFET has been demonstrated that conducts over 30A at a power dissipation of 200 W/cm² [5]. The state-of-the art at higher voltages is a 10 kV, 120 A module that parallels multiple 10 kV, 10A SiC DMOSFET die and 10 kV SiC JBS diode die. The modules has been integrated into an inverter for a compact 13.8kV to 465V/ 465/ $\sqrt{3}$ solid-state power substation (SSPS) rated at 1 MVA [6].

The issues for the SiC MOSFET development have included developing gate oxide growth with sufficiently low interface state density to provide motilities of greater than 60 cm²/V.s for 4H-SiC substrates, developing approaches to anneal implants in SiC without significant degradation of the SiC surface, and development of optimized junction terminations. In addition, the SiC MOSFET device or module is sometime designed to ensure that the build-in diode of the SiC p-well does not forward bias during free-wheeling operation. The primary consideration for ensuring that the p-well does not forward bias is the potential for nucleation of stacking faults on basal plane defects in the SiC epitaxial layer if minority carriers are injected from the p-well into the N-type epitaxial layer which degrades the forward voltage of the MOSFET [7]. One approach that has been developed to ensure the build-in body diode does not forward bias is to incorporate an Schottky diode in series with the sources [8].

The on-resistance of the SiC-DMOSFET is a combination of channel resistance, the resistance of the JFET region between the P-wells, the drift layer resistance, the substrate resistance, and the ohmic contact resistances. As the voltage rating of the devices increases, the drift layer resistance dominates the on-resistance of the devices and reducing the importance of high channel mobility and low JFET resistances [10].

B. SiC JFET

Significant advances have also been made is SiC Junction

F. J. Kub is with the Power Electron Branch, Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC 20375 USA (e-mail: fritz.kub@nrl.navy.mil).

Field Effect Transistors (JFET) shown in Figure . The SiC JFET was commercialized by Semisouth in 2011 with both 1200V and 1700V products, and also normally-on and normally-off products [9]. The 1700 V JFET has a maximum on-resistance of 63 m Ω [10].

The normally-on JFET operates by applying a negative voltage to the gate relative to the source which pinches off the vertical channel to turn-off the JFET. The normally-off JFET have the vertical channel pinched off for zero gate bias and a positive gate bias is applied relative to the source to turn on the device. The normally-off JFETs have a threshold voltage of approximately 1V [10]. The positive gate bias on the gate forward biases the gate to source junction injecting minority carriers source contact. The ability of the gate driver to be able to supply the forward bias current and charge the gate capacitance significantly affects turn-on and turn-off speed [11]. The low gate threshold voltage of the normally-off transistor requires a gate driver with a negative bias during the off time to provide noise immunity and to avoid inadvertently turning on the gate due to induced gate voltage spikes [11] Adding a capacitor across device gate-source terminal acts as a snubber and increases its immunity to unwanted switching [11].

Fig. 1. Simplified schematic of SiC JFET.

Whether the vertical channel is pinched off at zero gate bias or whether there is a currently flow at zero gate is determined by the device design that controls the width of the vertical fingers (d) between the two recessed gate trenches [11]. Because of the wider vertical channel, the normally-on JFET will have a higher current capability then the normally-off JFET for a given device area. Both the normally-on and the normally-off JFETs have a positive temperature coefficient for forward voltage which facilitates paralleling the devices in a module. The SiC JFET does not use a gate dielectric and the channel mobility is nearly that for bulk SiC. The SiC JFET also does not have a tail current in the turn-off waveform.

A normally-off JFET has been demonstrated with 1650 V avalanche voltage with 2.6 m Ω -cm² at 25 co for a 9mm² device area [12]. By combining these two devices i.e. recovery free SiC Schottky diodes SiC VJFET, significant improvement in overall efficiency, up to 99% overall efficiency, can be achieved [13]

Gate drivers that are used to drive silicon IGBTs can be used to drive the SiC JFET; however, n optimized driver specifically designed to drive the normally-off JFET can

significantly improve the switching performance of the SiC JFET. One such driver is a two-stage DC-coupled driver [6]. When an optimized driver is used, a reduction of 80% and 70% in turn-off time and switching loss is observed, respectively [11].

C. SiC Bipolar Transistor

Advantages of the SiC bipolar transistor are that it is a normally-off transistors, has low emitter to collect saturation voltage, low stored charge, does not have a current tail during turnoff, is suitable for high temperature operation because they are free of gate-oxide reliability issues, and has a positive temperature coefficient of on-resistance [14] which enables parallel of transistors. Several important issues for the SiC bipolar transistor are achieving high common-emitter current gain, susceptibility to degradation during operation if basal plane defects are present in the epitaxial layer, and the ability to achieve conductivity modulation in the collector [14].

Fig. 2. Schematic cross section of a fabricated 4H-SiC BJT and optical image of a fabricated single-finger BJT [15].

The current gain is strongly dependent on a number of material and surface passivation properties. To achieve high current gain, it is necessary to have achieve high minority carrier lifetime in the p-type base, to have low surface recombination velocity on the extrinsic base surface and the emitter sidewall, and to either not use a p-type ion implant for p-type base ohmic contact or to design the bipolar device so that the defects from the P-type implant are sufficiently separated from the emitter to not degrade the current gain. Significant advances have been made in achieving high bipolar current gain with the recent achievement of a common-emitter current gain of 247 for a SiC silicon-face and a common emitter current gain of 335 for the SiC carbon-face [15]. The techniques that were employed to achieve these high current gain values include a deep-level reduction process involving the uses of a 1150C oxidation to increase the minority carrier lifetime in the base and collector before and after an 1800C ion implant anneal, a continuous growth of the emitter epitaxial layer on the base p-type base without exposing the surface to air, a NO oxidation at 1300 °C was

used to minimize surface recombination on the extrinsic base surface and the emitter mesa sidewalls.

An additional approach that has been used to reduce the issue defects generated by the high temperature ion implant anneal which can decrease the common-emitter current gain is an implant free SiC bipolar process [16]. This process used a stepped high voltage junction termination instead of an implanted termination and did not use a p-type implant for ohmic contact. A triple layer Ni/Ti/Al metal was deposited for the base contact.

An example of the state-of-the-art of SiC bipolar transistors is an 18.4 mm², 1200 V, 50 A specific on-resistance of 3.5 mΩ cm² at 25 °C and 5.5 mΩ cm² at 150 °C corresponding to resistance of 24 mΩ and 46 mΩ [17]. Typical common-emitter current gains are 85 at room temperature and 50 at 150C. The high current gains were attributed to improved surface passivation. The device current density is approximately 330 A/cm², limited by the thermal resistance of the package. The switching loss for the SiC bipolar transistor was the same at 25C and 150C. Simulation of the switching loss comparing the SiC bipolar to a silicon IGBT for a boost DC/DC converter, the cooling requirements can be reduced by a factor of 4.3 compare to the cooling requirements for a silicon IGBT.

D. SiC IGBT

For applications requiring power switches with greater than approximately 10 kV blocking voltage, an SiC IGBT is considered to be a favorable device compared to a SiC MOSFET due to the conductivity modulation that can be obtained for SiC IGBT [18]. Both N-channel and P-channel high voltage IGBT have been demonstrated [18, 19]. The designation of N-channel or P-channel refers to the MOSFET transistor type. The N-channel IGBT has a N-channel MOSFET driver transistor and a PNP bipolar gain structure. The P-channel IGBT has a P-channel MOSFET driver transistor and an NPN bipolar gain structure. A 12kV P-channel IGBT with an on-resistance of 18.6 mΩcm² [1] has been demonstrated while the N-channel IGBT had an on-resistance of 22 mΩcm² [19].

Fig. 3. Schematic cross section of P-Channel SiC IGBT.

The P-channel IGBT had a slow turn-off because of the large amount of minority carrier charge that was stored in the NPN base layer due the high injection efficiency of the N+ substrate/N+ buffer while the N-channel IGBT had fast turn-off [14]. Both the N-channel and P-channel IGBT had a positive temperature coefficient of forward voltage with the P-channel characteristic having a more favorable forward voltage change with temperature.

Several advantages for the P-channel IGBT compared the N-channel IGBT include the ability to utilize a N-type SiC substrate and less demanding requirement of the carrier lifetime in IGBT base layer. The P-channel transistor had a mobility of 12 cm²/Vs. One consideration for high voltage IGBT is that the MOSFET channel mobility is a less significant contribution to the total resistance compared to the drift layer resistance. The advantage of the N-channel IGBT is that the technology that has been developed for growing N-type epitaxial layers and controlling minority carrier lifetime in epitaxial layer can be utilized, and the bias arrangement is similar to conventional silicon IGBTs. A significant issue for the N-channel IGBT is that a p-type SiC is typically required. P-type substrates are not available in large dimensions and production volumes and they also introduce high resistance in series to the device [20].

E. SiC GTO

The primary advantage of the SiC thyristor and GTO are for application requiring high current and high voltage. The SiC GTO is projected to the preferred power switching device for current handling capability larger than 1000 A and for blocking voltage greater than 10kV. The SiC GTO has a positive temperature coefficient which is a requirement to be able to parallel multiple SiC GTO devices in a module to achieve high current capability [14]. The SiC GTO is susceptible to degradation with operation if basal plane defects are present in the epitaxial layer.

Fig. 4. Cross section schematic of SiC thyristor.

A record 1x1 cm² size GTO with a breakdown voltage of 9kV has been demonstrated [21]. A forward drop of 3.7 V at

100 A (100 A/cm²) is measured at 25°C. For pulse power applications, a peak current of 12.8 kA conducted with a pulse width of 17.4 μs.

F. SiC Junction Barrier Schottky Diode

A high payoff application for the SiC Schottky or SiC JBS diode is the use as a free-wheeling diode with silicon IGBT switch. The SiC Schottky diode plays a large role in reducing the turn-on loss of the silicon switch. The charge stored in the silicon free-wheeling diode produces a significant reverse recovery current in the transistor turning on and thus produces a large turn-on energy loss. Since the SiC Schottky diode has significantly reduced stored charge in the base region of the diode, the turn-on loss of the silicon switch is greatly reduced. In a study that made a one-to-one comparison of the free-wheeling operation of a SiC JBS diode to a silicon PiN diode for use with a 4500 V silicon IGBT, the SiC JBS diode has approximately a factor of 22 less reverse recovery charge at room temperature and is temperature independent to 125C [1]. The replacement of a silicon diode with a SiC JBS diode results in greater than a factor of 4 reduction in the 4500V IGBT turn-on loss and factor of 20 reduction in current stress. The switching loss calculations show that the IGBT/SiC JBS diode pair can operate at 50 percent higher current level than the IGBT/ silicon Pin diode pair.

G. Conclusion

The progress and key issues with SiC power devices was reviewed. Both SiC MOSFETs and JFETs have demonstrated significant performance improvements compared to silicon IGBTs. Higher voltage SiC MOSFET and JFETs have been demonstrated and have the promise to find commercial application. Significant advances have been made in understanding and solving the issues related to achieving high current gain in SiC bipolar transistors. SiC IGBT will be promising power devices above 10 kV blocking voltage and SiC GTO have promise for applications requiring high current and high voltage. Advances in SiC substrate and epitaxial material growth will contribute significantly to advances in SiC devices.

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IV. BIOGRAPHIES

Francis J. Kub (S'75,M'78, SM'09, F'11) received the B.S. degree in Engineering Physics from the South Dakota State University, Brookings, in 1972, the M.S.E.E. degree from the University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, in 1976, and the Ph.D. degree in Electrical Engineering from the University of Maryland, College Park, in 1985. In 1974, he joined Westinghouse, Linthicum, Maryland as a process integration engineer and was promoted to Fellow Engineer. In 1985, he joined the Naval

Research Laboratory in Washington, DC, where he is currently the Head of the Power Electronics Branch. His research interest have included SiC and GaN power devices, wafer bonding for novel substrates, analog VLSI circuit, photodetector array design, Charge Coupled Device integration, and advanced VLSI integration.

Dr. Kub has served on the International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices in 2003 and the Imager and Sensor Subcommittee of the International Solid State Circuits Conference from 1994 to 2002. He was Associate Editor of IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON CIRCUIT AND SYSTEMS from 1997 to 1999. He has more than 100 publications and has been awarded 40 patents. He received the Distinguished Engineer Award from South Dakota State University in 2010